

Preferential solvation effect on the kinetics of oxidation of *para*-substituted anilines by tetramethylammonium fluorochromate

M. Karthikeyan^a, S. Ghamami^b, D. S. Bhuvaneshwari^a and K. P. Elango^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Gandhigram Rural University, Gandhigram-624 302, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : drkpelango@rediffmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Imam Khomeini International University, Ghazvin, Iran

Manuscript received 11 December 2006, accepted 14 February 2007

Abstract : Tetramethylammonium fluorochromate (TMAFC) oxidation of *para*-substituted anilines, in varying mole fractions of benzene in 2-methylpropan-2-ol, in the presence of *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (PTS) is first-order in TMAFC and PTS and is zero-order with respect to substrate. The TMAFC oxidation of six *para*-substituted anilines at 298–308 K complies with the isokinetic relationship but not to any of the linear free energy relationships; the isokinetic temperature lies within the experimental range. The specific rate of oxidizing species-anilines reaction correlates with Brown-Okamoto's substituent constants affording negative reaction constant. The correlation of rate data with macroscopic solvent parameters such as ϵ_r and E_T^N is satisfactory while correlation with Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic parameters (α , β , π^*) suggests that the specific solute-solvent interactions play a major role in governing the reactivity.

Keywords : Solvation, oxidation, anilines.

The study of solute-solvent interactions in binary solvent mixtures is more complex than in pure solvents. In a pure solvent the composition of the microsphere of solvation of a solute, the so called cybotatic region, is the same as in the bulk solvent, but in binary mixtures the composition in this microsphere can be different. The solute can interact to a different degree with the components of the mixture, and this difference in the interactions is reflected in the composition of the microsphere of solvation. The effect of varying the composition of the mixture from the bulk solvent to the solvation sphere is called preferential solvation¹. The kinetics of oxidation of organic compounds in non-aqueous and aquo-organic solvent mixtures has revealed the important role of non-specific and specific solvent effects on reactivity². Furthermore, one of the important tools in deciding the mechanism of reactions is the study of substituent effects and thermodynamic parameters³.

Aniline and its derivatives are used as intermediates for the manufacturing of various organic compounds such as colorants, agro-chemicals, pharmaceuticals etc.⁴. It has been found to be widely distributed in an aqueous environment and cause teratosis in aquatic species⁵. Anilines (aromatic amines) are the most widespread and principal contaminants of industrial wastewaters. These comprise an important class of environmental contaminants. The reaction pathways of aromatic amines in natural systems are dominated by redox reactions with soil and sediment constituents. Better understanding of the mechanism of oxidation of such

compounds/contaminants to harmless products is the important goal for basic research and industrial applications, hence, the present study.

Keeping this in view, a systematic study of various LFERs and isokinetic relationship has been made to establish the role of solvent and substituents on reactivity and to decide the nature of the mechanism followed in the oxidation of *para*-substituted anilines by tetramethylammonium fluorochromate (TMAFC) in benzene/2-methylpropan-2-ol mixtures of varying compositions. This mixture is so chosen that by varying the mole fraction of the constituent solvents, the hydrogen bonding properties of the medium can be varied in a smooth and continuous manner since 2-methylpropan-2-ol is classified as a typical hydrogen bond donor (HBD) and benzene as a typical non-hydrogen bond donor (non-HBD) solvent⁶.

Results and discussion

Kinetic results : The kinetics of oxidation of unsubstituted and *para*-(Me, OMe, NO₂, Br, Cl) substituted anilines were carried out under pseudo-first-order conditions with [substrate] \gg [TMAFC] in varying mole fractions of benzene in 2-methylpropan-2-ol. The observed rate constants are given in Table 1. The selection of the mole fractions was based on the fact that the solvatochromic parameters employed in the present study for correlation analysis are available in the literature¹. The overall reaction is represented as follows.

The first-order dependence of the reaction on TMAFC is obvious from the linearity ($r \geq 0.90$) of plots of $\log [\text{TMAFC}]$ versus time. Further, the pseudo-first-order rate constants, k_{obs} , do not depend on the initial concentration of TMAFC (Table 2). The oxidation is zero-order in the substrate (Table 2) The oxidation process is slow, but is catalyzed in the presence of PTS, and the reaction proceeds at a comfortable rate. The oxidation rate increases with increasing [PTS] and a plot of k_{obs} versus [PTS] is a straight line passing through the origin ($r = 0.987$, $sd = 0.0005$). The reaction did not promote polymerization of acrylonitrile indicating absence of free radicals

Table 1. Pseudo-first-order rate constants ($10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$, s^{-1}) for the oxidation of *para*-substituted anilines by TMAFC at 298 K

Mole fraction of benzene	Substituent in aniline moiety					
	H	<i>p</i> -Me	<i>p</i> -OMe	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br
0.0595	7.28	1.07	151.4	0.83	6.32	0.34
0.0985	8.22	1.14	202.7	3.41	7.14	0.34
0.1292	10.43	1.36	174.0	33.20	11.38	0.39
0.1514	13.95	11.30	163.0	28.82	12.14	0.59
0.1873	15.66	47.46	256.6	33.22	25.58	1.46
0.3213	35.46	78.89	394.7	37.20	27.76	1.51
0.4223	36.15	237.18	575.0	83.58	29.55	36.57
0.5222	95.17	528.95	1109.0	650.70	31.89	58.99
0.6786	115.17	578.59	fast	913.90	147.60	76.48
0.8663	216.27	636.97	fast	fast	241.60	927.80

Table 2. Pseudo-first-order rate constants for the oxidation of aniline by TMAFC at 298 K in benzene/2-methylpropan-2-ol mixture

Mole fraction of benzene	Substituent	$10^2[\text{Sub}]$	$10^3[\text{TMAFC}]$	$10^2[\text{TsOH}]$	$10^5 k_{\text{obs}} \text{ s}^{-1}$	
		(M)	(M)	(M)		
0.5222	<i>p</i> -Me	0.5	1.0	2.0	525	
		1.0	1.0	2.0	524	
		2.0	1.0	2.0	528	
		3.0	1.0	2.0	525	
	H	0.5	1.0	2.0	94	
		1.0	1.0	2.0	95	
		2.0	1.0	2.0	95	
		3.0	1.0	2.0	92	
	0.5222	H	2.0	1.0	2.0	95
			2.0	1.25	2.0	96
			2.0	1.50	2.0	94
			2.0	1.75	2.0	97
0.5222	H	2.0	1.0	1.5	41	
		2.0	1.0	2.0	95	
		2.0	1.0	2.5	164	
		2.0	1.0	3.0	210	

Activation parameters : The activation parameters were calculated from k_{obs} , at 298, 303 and 308 K using Eyring plots and are collected in Table 3. The oxidation is neither isoenthalpic nor isoentropic but complies with the compensation law also known as isokinetic relationship (eq (1)),

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H^\circ + \beta \Delta S^\ddagger \quad (1)$$

The isokinetic temperature is the temperature at which all the compounds of the series react equally fast. Also, at the isokinetic temperature the variation of substituent has no influence on the free energy of activation. In an isoentropic oxidation the isokinetic temperature lies at infinite and only enthalpy of activation determines the reactivity. The isokinetic temperature is zero for an isoenthalpic series and the reactivity is determined by the entropy of activation⁷ In the present oxidation the activation enthalpy is linearly related to activation entropy as shown in Fig. 1 (In 0.4229 mole fraction, $r = 0.996$, $sd = 3.09$, isokinetic temperature = 312 ± 14 K). The operation of isokinetic relationship reveals that all the substituted anilines examined are oxidized through a common mechanism.

Table 3. Effect of temperature on the rate of oxidation of substituted anilines by TMAFC in 0.4223 mole fraction of benzene and activation parameters for the oxidation

Substituent	Rate constants $10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1})			ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger
	298 K	303 K	308 K			
H	36	41	45	14	-262	92.6
<i>p</i> -Me	237	242	316	19	-230	87.9
<i>p</i> -OMe	575	638	856	27	-195	85.9
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	83	146	206	66	-79	90.5
<i>p</i> -Cl	29	46	87	81	-40	93.2
<i>p</i> -Br	36	52	95	71	-71	92.6

[Substrate] = $2 \times 10^{-2} M$, [TMAFC] = $1 \times 10^{-3} M$, [PTS] = $2 \times 10^{-2} M$
 ΔH^\ddagger in kJ mol^{-1} , ΔS^\ddagger in $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, ΔG^\ddagger in kJ mol^{-1}

The entropies and enthalpies of activation were also calculated for the oxidation of aniline in all the solvent mixtures investigated (Table 4). The existence of a linear relationship ($r = 0.995$, $sd = 3.38$, isokinetic temperature = 282 ± 10 K) between ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger indicates that a single mechanism is operating in all the solvent systems studied (Fig. 2). A perusal of data in Table 4 indicates that values of ΔS^\ddagger vary from 52 to $-320 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ which clearly suggests that the extent of solvation of the activated complex is different in different solvent mixtures. The change of mole fraction from 0.0595 to 0.8663 causes 216-fold rate acceleration for the reaction which corresponds to a decrease in ΔG^\ddagger of 12.1 kJ mol^{-1} . The largest k_{obs} values are obtained in the relatively more apolar solvent mixture. This observation can be

Fig. 1. The isokinetic plot for the oxidation of anilines by TMAFC in 0.4223 mole fraction of benzene in 2-methylpropan-2-ol

rationalized because polar solvents will have some structure corresponding to the orientation of the dipolar solvent molecules due to intermolecular solvent-solvent interactions. In less polar solvents, however, which have only a small or no dipole moment, the solvent molecules will be relatively unoriented. Hence, it is presumed that, in the present study, solvent-solvent interactions play a significant role, in addition to, solute-solvent interactions in governing the rate of the reaction⁶.

Table 4. Thermodynamic parameters and relative rate constants at 298 K for the oxidation of unsubstituted aniline by TMAFC in different mole fraction of benzene in 2-methylpropan-2-ol

Mole fraction	ϵ_r	$10^5 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$	$k_{\text{obs}}^{\text{rel}}$	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger
0.0595	11.85	1.0	1	81	-62	99.6
0.0985	11.48	8.2	8	1	-320	96.4
0.1292	11.15	10.4	10	107	44	93.8
0.1514	10.94	13.9	14	106	43	93.3
0.1873	10.67	15.7	16	107	48	93.0
0.3213	9.24	36.5	36	92	5	94.1
0.4223	8.20	36.1	36	14	-262	92.6
0.5222	7.17	95.2	95	71	-61	89.5
0.6786	5.66	115.2	115	77	-44	89.9
0.8663	3.70	216.3	216	103	52	87.5

ΔH^\ddagger in kJ mol^{-1} ; ΔS^\ddagger in $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$; ΔG^\ddagger in kJ mol^{-1}

Structure-reactivity correlation: The effect of substituents on the oxidation rate was studied with six *para*-substituted anilines in different mole fractions of benzene in 2-methylpropan-2-ol. The results given in Table 1 reveal that the rate constants vary with substrate in a particular solvent mixture, through the rate of the reaction is independent of [substrate]. This may be due to the fact that because of

difference in polarity of different anilines, the extent of solvation should be different and hence the experimental values of rate constants may be different for different anilines as observed by us in the present study. The rate data failed to conform to either the usual Hammett equation or modified ones; plots of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus substituent constants such as σ , σ^+ and σ^- are non-linear (not shown). The dual substituent parameter (DSP) equations⁸ also failed to correlate the rate data with the substituent.

Fig. 2. The isokinetic plot for the oxidation of unsubstituted aniline in all the mole fractions under investigation

Anilines in basic and neutral media are present as free bases but in acid medium exist in dual forms, the free bases and the conjugate acids. And, the ratio of the concentrations of the free bases to the conjugate acid ($[\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2]/[\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_3^+]$) depends on the $\text{p}K_a$ of the aniline and the acidity of the medium. The reported oxidation of anilines, in the present study, were carried out under pseudo-first-order conditions ($[\text{anilines}] \gg [\text{TMAFC}]$), and the concentration of TMAFC at different reaction times were determined by titrimetry. The pseudo-first-order rate constants (k_{obs}) were obtained from the least-squares slopes of $\log [\text{TMAFC}]$ versus time plots, and the second-order rate constants are $k' = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{aniline}]_T$ where $[\text{aniline}]_T$ is the total concentration of aniline. Since the $\text{p}K_a$ varies from 5.35 (*p*-OMe) to 1.01 (*p*-NO₂) and molecular anilines are the reactive species (nucleophile), the reported $k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{aniline}]_T$ values are not the rate constants of the oxidant-molecular aniline reactions. And the analysis of k_{obs} and $k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{aniline}]_T$ in terms of the Hammett and modified Hammett equations is erroneous.

Hence, the specific reaction rates of molecular anilines with the oxidant ($k_2 = k' (K_a + [\text{H}^+]/K_a)$) have been obtained, as reported earlier for the oxidation of anilines by

percarbonate⁹, imidazolium fluorochromate¹⁰ and perborate⁷ and correlated in terms of the structure-reactivity relationships. In the reactions of anilines in acid medium, as the free bases are the nucleophiles, the specific reaction rates of anilines are to be obtained using the concentrations of the free bases but not the total concentrations of anilines. The concentrations of the free bases, in the present study, have been deduced as reported earlier by adopting the similar approximations⁹. The specific rates of the oxidant-molecular aniline reactions are collected in Table 5.

Table 5. Specific rate (k_2 , $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$) of the oxidant-molecular aniline reaction at 298 K

Mole fraction of benzene	Substituent in aniline moiety					
	H	<i>p</i> -Me	<i>p</i> -OMe	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br
0.0595	0.07	2.34	64.50	0.01	0.18	0.08
0.0985	0.56	2.50	86.36	0.01	0.20	0.08
0.1292	0.71	2.98	74.13	0.03	0.32	0.09
0.1514	0.94	2.47	69.44	0.03	0.38	0.13
0.1873	1.06	10.37	109.07	0.03	0.73	0.33
0.3213	2.48	17.24	167.86	0.03	0.79	0.33
0.4223	2.46	51.89	244.98	0.07	0.85	0.82
0.5222	6.47	115.69	472.91	0.58	0.91	1.32
0.6786	7.83	126.57	fast	0.81	4.22	1.71
0.8663	14.70	139.32	fast	fast	6.92	20.72

The specific rates of the rate limiting step of *para*-substituted anilines correlate satisfactorily with the Brown-Okamoto equation and a representative plot is given in Fig. 3. Negative reaction constants show the formation of positive charged transition state. Regression analysis k_2 shows an improved correlation ($100r^2 > 75\%$) with σ^+ , when compared to the same using k_{obs} ($100r^2 < 43\%$). Multiple correlation analysis reveals that dual substituent parameter (DSP) equation with explanatory variables F and R governs fairly the variation of k_2 with *para*-substituents. The reaction coefficients of field and resonance effects are negative and the percentage contributions of these two terms are almost equal, as expected for *para*-substituents^{7,9}. Parallel to simple linear correlation results, the correlation of k_2 with substituent constants ($100r^2 > 76\%$), through multiple correlation equations, are better than those with k_{obs} ($100r^2 < 47\%$).

Solvent-reactivity correlation: The title reaction has been studied in varying mole fractions of benzene in 2-methylpropan-2-ol with a view to understand the effect of preferential solvation on the reactivity. The separation of solvent effects on rate into initial-state and transition-state contributions and also the rationalization of various solvent-solute interactions have been done, by adopting the technique of correlation analysis; using $\log k^2$ values¹¹.

The correlation of $\log k_2$ values with the inverse of the relative permittivity¹² is just satisfactory ($0.785 < r < 0.983$, $0.06 < sd < 0.49$). Similarly, the correlation of $\log k_2$ with one of the more successful solvent polarity indices, Reichardt's⁶ E_T^N , is also satisfactory ($0.892 < r < 0.968$, $0.08 < sd < 0.37$). A representative plot is shown in Fig. 4. The results of these correlations reveal the operation of selective or preferential solvation which includes both non-specific solute-solvent association caused by dielectric enrichment in the solvation shell of solute ions or dipolar solute molecules and specific solute-solvent association such as hydrogen bonding or EPD/EPA interactions⁶.

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log k_2$ versus σ^+ .

To explain this type of dual dependency of rate on solvent the kinetic data were correlated with Kamlet-Taft's¹³ solvatochromic parameters in the form of the following LSER,

$$\log k = A_0 + s\pi^* + a\alpha + b\beta \quad (2)$$

where,

π^* – solvent dipolarity/polarizability,

α – solvent hydrogen bond donor acidity (HBD),

β – solvent hydrogen bond acceptor basicity.

The regression coefficients s , a and b measure the relative susceptibilities of the solvent dependent solute property $\log k_2$ to the indicated solvent parameters. The solvatochromic parameters employed in the present study were taken from the literature and are estimated based on the preferential solvation model¹. The $\log k_2$ values show a good correlation (Table 6) with solvent via the above LSER with an explained variance of ca. 90%. Such a good correlation indicates the existence of both specific and non-specific solute-solvent interactions in the present system.

Fig. 4. Plot of $\log k_2$ versus E_T^N .

The statistical results of the correlation and weighted percentage contributions of the solvatochromic parameters are presented in Table 6. The observation of this multiple regression analysis leads to the following conclusions. (i) The weighted percentage contributions of the solvatochromic parameters indicate that the specific solvent-solvent-solute interactions, as indicated by P_α and P_β , play a major role in governing the rate of the oxidation process. (ii) The average value of the contribution of the solvent HBD acidity, α , to the total solvent effects is dominant. Based on the two-step preferential solvation model, proposed by Skwierczynski and Connors¹⁴, it was established that the properties of 2-methylpropan-2-ol/benzene mixtures are very close to the average of the properties of the two solvents, except for the hydrogen bond acidity α , which seems to be equal to that of pure benzene (i.e. *ca.* zero)¹. Hence with increase in mole fraction of benzene in the mixture there is a drastic decrease in the hydrogen bond acidity, α , of the medium and hence increase in rate of the reaction as indicated by the negative sign of coefficient of this term. (iii) Likewise, as benzene has no hydrogen bonding properties, with increase in mole fraction of benzene in the mixture the hydrogen bond basicity, β , decreases¹, which in turn enhances the rate of the oxidation. (iv) As indicated by P_{π^*} , solvent dipolarity/polarizability also contributes to the rate to an appreciable extent. Since benzene is a more polarizable solvent ($\delta = 1$) than 2-methylpropan-2-ol ($\delta = 0$), an increase in its mole fraction in the mixture increases the polarizability of the medium and consequently increases the rate of the reaction.

Table 6. Statistical results and weighted percentage contributions for the correlation of rate of oxidation (k_2) of substituted anilines by TMAFC with Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic parameters α , β and π^*

Substituent	R^2	sd	a	b	s	P_α	P_β	P_{π^*}
H	0.8127	0.55	-5.53	-2.04	-3.39	50	27	28
<i>p</i> -Me	0.9293	0.25	-12.31	0.86	4.10	71	5	24
<i>p</i> -OMe	0.9519	0.09	-1.16	-2.37	1.36	24	48	28
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.8601	0.37	3.14	-5.32	6.26	21	36	43
<i>p</i> -Cl	0.9321	0.17	-1.22	-2.55	1.70	22	47	31
<i>p</i> -Br	0.9276	0.26	5.01	-5.85	-2.68	37	43	20

a , b and s – Coefficients in eq. (2).

Mechanism: The results of structure-reactivity correlation indicate that molecular anilines are the reactive species¹⁵. Negative reaction constants indicate the formation of a positively charged transition state. In non-aqueous media Cr^{VI} reagents complex with the aniline and the reaction exhibits Michaelis-Menten kinetics with respect to the substrate. Such a complex formation is supported by the observed negative entropy of activation. If the formation constant (K) of the oxidant-substrate complex is large the oxidation is to exhibit zero-order dependence on [substrate]¹⁶. Similar observations were recorded in the oxidation of anilines by a Cr^{VI} oxidant in the solvent mixture under investigation¹⁷. Based on the forgoing results a possible mechanism has been proposed for the oxidation of anilines by TMAFC (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The above mechanism leads to, under the condition that the formation constant (K) of the oxidant-substrate complex is large, the following rate law,

$$-d[\text{NDC}]/dt = k [\text{NDC}][\text{PTS}]$$

The above scheme accounts for the observed orders. The formation of the reaction product azobenzene may follow, through N-attack, the Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

Conclusion: The oxidation of aniline by TMAFC is first-order with respect to [TMAFC], [acid] and zero-order with

respect to [sub]. Under the experimental conditions anilines are oxidized to azobenzene. Negative reaction constants indicate the formation of positive charged transition state. The reaction is highly influenced by varying the mole fraction of benzene in 2-methylpropan-2-ol. Linear and multiple regression analysis may be used to separate and quantify the specific and non-specific solvational effects on the oxidation of anilines by TMAFC. Using the method the significance of those solvent-solvent-solute interactions and the reactivity has been established. From the regression coefficients information on the solvent-reactant and the solvent-transition state interactions is obtained.

Experimental

Materials and kinetic measurements : All the chemicals and solvents used were of analytical grade. The solid anilines were used as such and the liquid anilines were used after vacuum distillation. TMAFC was prepared by a reported method¹⁸ and its purity was checked by an iodometric method.

The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first-order conditions by keeping an excess of substrate over TMAFC in the presence of *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (PTS). The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating the unconsumed oxidant iodometrically at 25, 30, 35 (± 0.1) °C. The rate constants were determined by the least squares method, from the linear plots ($r \geq 0.90$) of \log [TMAFC] versus time. Replicate runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by carrying out several sets of experiments with varying amounts of [TMAFC] largely in excess over [substrate]. The estimation of unconsumed TMAFC showed that three moles of the substrate react with two moles of TMAFC. For product analysis TMAFC was allowed to react with aniline, under kinetic conditions, for 24 h. After completion of the reaction the oxidation product was analyzed using preparative TLC on silica gel, which yielded azobenzene. The product azobenzene was identified by its melting point [66 °C (lit. 68 °C)], IR and UV spectra. The spectra are super impossible with those of the authentic sample; UV (EtOH) $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 320$ nm.

Data analysis : Correlation analyses were carried out using Microcal Origin (version 6) computer software. The goodness of fit was discussed using correlation coefficient (r in the case of simple linear regression and R in the case of multiple linear regression) and standard deviation, sd . The percentage contribution (P_x) of a parameter to the total effect on reactivity was computed using the regression coefficient of each parameter as reported earlier¹⁹.

References

1. E. Bosch, F. Rived and M. Roses, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1996, 2177.
2. J. R. C. Ramyavijayakumari and K. P. Elango, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 834; S. Saravanakanna and K. P. Elango, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2002, **34**, 585; G. Fatimajayanthi and K. P. Elango, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2003, **35**, 154; K. P. Elango, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **66**, 359; D. S. Bhuvaneshwari, J. Bincy, M. Pandeewaran and K. P. Elango, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 1.
3. J. Shorter, "Correlation Analysis of Organic Reactivity", Research Student Press, Letchworth, 1982.
4. S. Zok, G. Gorege, W. Kalsch and R. Nagel, *Sci. Total Environ.*, 1991, **109/110**, 411.
5. F. S. H. Abram and I. R. Sims, *Water Res.*, 1982, **16**, 1309; A. L. Walpole and M. H. C. Williams, *Brit. Med. Bull.*, 1958, **14**, 141; W. S. Beck, "Hematology", The MIT Press, 1998, 184.
6. C. Reichardt, "Solvents and Solvent Effects in Organic Chemistry", VCH, Weinheim, 1988.
7. C. Karunakaran and P. N. Palanisamy, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1997, **127**, 559.
8. S. K. Dayal, S. Ehrenson and R. W. Taft, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 9113; C. G. Swain, S. H. Unger, N. R. Rosenquist and M. S. Swain, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **105**, 492.
9. C. Karunakaran and R. Kamalam, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2002, **67**, 1118.
10. D. S. Bhuvaneshwari and K. P. Elango, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2006, **38**, 166.
11. M. H. Abraham, P. L. Grellier, J. M. Abboud, R. M. Doherty and R. M. Taft, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1988, **66**, 2673.
12. E. S. Amis and J. I. Hinton, "Solvent Effect of Chemical Phenomena", Academic Press, New York, 1973.
13. M. J. Kamlet, J. M. Abboud and M. H. Abraham, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, **48**, 2877.
14. R. D. Skwierczynski and K. A. Connors, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1994, 467.
15. C. Karunakaran and R. Kamalam, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 2002, 2011.
16. C. Karunakaran and V. Chidambaranathan, *Croatica Chim. Acta*, 2001, **74**, 51.
17. D. S. Bhuvaneshwari and K. P. Elango, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 2005, **60b**, 1105.
18. A. R. Mahjoub, S. Ghamami and M. Z. Kassae, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2003, **44**, 4555.
19. C. Reichardt, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. (Eng.)*, 1979, **18**, 98.